

Military Training, Education and Combat Training in the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies

Djurabayev Rustam Turabbayevich

Lecturer, Department of Combat Training, Institute of Advanced Training of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan,
Lieutenant Colonel

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Abstract: The article provides a scientific analysis of the theoretical and practical aspects of combat training in the activities of internal affairs bodies as one of the necessary means of ensuring public safety in the country. Based on the norms of legislation regulating the educational process, taking into account the peculiarities of the process of training personnel of internal affairs bodies at the Academy and the Institute of Advanced Training of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the directions of development of patriotic education in the process of combat training for cadets and trainees as future highly qualified law enforcement officers are considered.

Keywords: combat training, patriotic education, cadet, listener, internal affairs bodies, academy, institute of advanced training.

At all stages of the development of society, the ability to find common ground for all forces confidently and decisively fighting to ensure public safety of the state and society is of particular importance. This is one of the urgent and important tasks of our time. The internal affairs bodies as a law enforcement agency are a state structure that ensures the security of the individual, society and the state. Only with combat-ready law enforcement agencies and the armed forces of the country, ready to perform any assigned service and combat tasks, can we count on strengthening the statehood, as well as strengthening the position of our state in the international arena [1]. The development of the internal affairs bodies (IAB) as one of the law enforcement agencies of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the present stage is a new page in their formation, development, and a full-scale reform of the entire IAB system is currently underway.

However, it is impossible to imagine a full-fledged reform of the IAB without changing the system of military training, education and combat training in the activities of IAB employees, the formation of their moral, fighting spirit, moral and military-professional qualities that will allow them to perform assigned service and combat tasks at any time and in any conditions. Military training, education and combat training in the activities of the employees of the Internal Affairs Bodies is a set of their targeted activities as a state structure, governing bodies and officials of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the formation and development of military personnel in accordance with the requirements of creating a modern military organization of the state. Military training, education and combat training in the activities of the Internal Affairs Bodies is a priority area of service and combat activities of employees [2]. The main goal of military training, education and combat training in the activities of the Internal Affairs Bodies is the formation

and development of the qualities and attitudes of a patriot, professional and highly moral person in employees.

In the system of military education, training and combat training in the activities of the Internal Affairs Directorate employees includes several areas:

- 1) state-patriotic education - this is the influence on the employees of the Internal Affairs Directorate with the aim of forming and developing an individual with the qualities of a patriot, capable of actively participating in strengthening and improving the foundations of society, prepared for the successful implementation of tasks related to ensuring public safety of the individual, society and the state.
- 2) military education - the process of systematic and purposeful influence on the spiritual and physical development of the employees of the Internal Affairs Directorate in order to prepare them to protect public safety.
- 3) moral education - influencing the consciousness, feelings and will of the employees of the Internal Affairs Directorate in order to form in them the necessary spiritual and moral traits and qualities.
- 4) legal education - purposeful and systematic influence on the consciousness, feelings and psychology of the employees of the Internal Affairs Directorate in order to form in them stable legal ideas, convictions and feelings, instilling in them a high legal culture, skills and habits of active lawful behavior.

For successful implementation of the above-mentioned areas of military training, education and combat training in the activities of the employees of the Internal Affairs Directorate [3, p. 147-148] duty to serve the people and gain people's trust. At present, conditions are being created to ensure the observance of human rights and freedoms, their full life and well-being. Must be formed in the consciousness of each employee of the Internal Affairs Directorate, absorbed into his flesh and blood, become the main motto of his official activities dedicated to ensuring peace and tranquility of the people, the safety of citizens, their protection from any encroachments. That is why each cadet and listener studying at the Academy and the Institute for Advanced Studies of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the process of training and education must justify the trust placed in him, i.e. honestly and tirelessly work on himself, be faithful to the chosen profession, the people, the President, the Motherland, conscientiously perform official duties. Cadets and students must have developed qualities that ensure respect for the rights and freedoms of citizens and the formation of the necessary professional skills, as well as practical experience for their use in everyday service activities.

The effectiveness of activities in the field of certain tasks to ensure protection from various encroachments, the safety of citizens, peace and tranquility of Uzbekistan is initially associated with the level of qualification of the specialists being trained. Only a highly qualified employee will be able to find an opportunity to effectively achieve the set goal in any situation.

Therefore, from the first days of independence, when implementing such tasks as ensuring peace and tranquility, the safety of citizens, their protection from various encroachments, special attention is paid to the training of highly qualified specialists for the Internal Affairs Directorate.

Serving the people, gaining people's trust and training highly qualified personnel is a very complex, continuous and indivisible process. Its complexity is connected, firstly, with the fact that all layers of society participate in this process, secondly, that the situation in all spheres of public life of society has a direct impact on it, thirdly, today the influence and number of various kinds of threats affecting this process is increasing. Therefore, the

training of highly qualified specialists for the Internal Affairs Directorate, capable of ensuring peace and tranquility, the safety of citizens, their protection from various kinds of encroachments, requires selfless and tireless work from the teaching staff and curators of educational institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs.

Based on this simple requirement, military training, education and combat training in the activities of the employees of the Internal Affairs Bodies is carried out in relation to harmoniously developed, living a full conscious life, able to think independently and broadly, should be recognized as the main goal and task of the educational and upbringing sphere. And this requires harmonious education and upbringing. Responsible for the education and upbringing of full-fledged specialists of the Internal Affairs Bodies are, first of all, their leaders, especially the services for working with personnel, as well as the teaching staff and mentors of educational institutions. In order to achieve positive results in the training of worthy personnel with the necessary knowledge, skills and experience, capable of honorably fulfilling their official duty and gaining public trust, it is necessary to ensure the participation in the educational process of representatives staffing the internal affairs bodies at the local level. This also applies to the sectoral services of the Ministry of Internal Affairs interacting with state and public organizations [4, p. 8-9]. Today, the question of what qualities an employee of the Internal Affairs Directorate should have to successfully perform his official duty and gain public trust remains very relevant. Some believe that it is enough for a specialist to have perfect command of his narrow specialty. However, it should be noted that today it is not enough to be a highly qualified specialist in his field; in order to gain public trust, among other things, spiritual, political, and intellectual perfection will be required.

Based on the requirements of the present time, it should be noted that the employees of the Internal Affairs Directorate being trained must be able to perform their official duty in any situation, gain public trust, avoid abuses, and become not only highly professional personnel, but also be spiritually, intellectually, psychologically, politically, ideologically, physically, and professionally mature.

The process of forming, strengthening, and developing the necessary qualities of a highly qualified specialist is a very complex and multifaceted process, interconnected with many factors and problems [5, p. 173-174]. At the Academy and the Institute for Advanced Studies, selection of candidates for training, as well as the formation, development, strengthening and establishment in the process of training of cadets and students of the qualities necessary for an employee of the Internal Affairs Directorate to successfully perform his professional activities. This is necessary for high-quality service to the people and winning the people's trust, carried out in stages, in an inseparable interconnectedness and logical sequence.

To form spiritual, psychological, political, ideological maturity in cadets and students of the Academy and the Institute for Advanced Studies in the process of studying social and humanitarian sciences. In the process of training, they study legal sciences to acquire legal, professional maturity. When studying special disciplines - physical and combat training, it is necessary to achieve the formation and strengthening of theoretical knowledge, practical skills and experience in future law enforcement officers. In addition, educational activities carried out by the drill unit of the Academy and the Institute for Advanced Studies, the personnel service and its structural divisions provide direct assistance in the formation, strengthening and development of the necessary knowledge, practical skills and experience in students and cadets, necessary for the subsequent performance of official duties.

The educational activities carried out by these divisions, on the one hand, serve to identify and develop organizational skills in cadets and students. Also for the acquisition of such qualities as initiative, loyalty. On the other hand, this allows for the possibility of preventing

and eliminating the causes and conditions that create all sorts of obstacles to the full performance of their professional duty by employees of the Internal Affairs Directorate.

A major role in the formation and strengthening of such qualities in cadets and students as loyalty to the people, the Motherland, the President, the profession, initiative, dedication, organizational skills, as well as practical skills in their application, necessary for an employee of the Internal Affairs Directorate to successfully perform his professional activities.

The main factors in achieving positive results in the sphere of formation and development of human qualities in cadets and students of the Academy and the Institute for Advanced Studies, instilling in them professional knowledge and skills necessary for an employee of the Internal Affairs Directorate to successfully perform his professional activities, are the continuity, phased nature, interconnectedness and logical sequence of the training process.

In addition, another important factor in achieving positive results in this area is the cooperation between the teaching staff, mentors who work with cadets and students after school hours, as well as representatives of public organizations.

Education cannot be separated from upbringing, just as upbringing cannot be separated from education - this is Eastern wisdom, the life philosophy of the East. Violation of these requirements, failure to use the above factors and opportunities in the educational process will inevitably lead to various negative consequences.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the education of personnel and the training of mature, highly qualified specialists for the Internal Affairs Directorate, capable of honorably fulfilling their professional duty of serving the people and gaining people's trust, has always been and remains a very complex and responsible matter. Therefore, the employees of the Internal Affairs Directorate, tirelessly working to expand their worldview, opening up new horizons, new directions in the protection of public safety, taking on the burden of performing these tasks. In order for them to achieve effective results, it is necessary to fully support their aspirations in practical actions that require great persistence, perseverance, knowledge and experience.

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